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GEO-STUDIES FORUM

An International Journal of Environmental and Policy Issues

**Department of Geography and Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Sciences,
University of Ilorin, Nigeria**

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Address: Department of Geography & Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Science, University of Ilorin, Nigeria.

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USE OF MOTORCYCLE AS ALTERNATIVE MEANS OF TRANSPORT IN OGBOMOSO, NIGERIA

¹Saka Nurudeen, ²Raji Abdulquadri Akande & ³Taiwo Luqman Adedeji

¹ & ²Ladoke Akintola University of Technology, Department of Urban and Regional Planning, Faculty of Environmental Sciences, P.M.B. 4000, Ogbomoso, Nigeria

³Tertiary Education Trust Fund (Tetfund), Zambezi Crescent, Off Aguiyi Ironsi Street, Maitama, Abuja, Nigeria

Corresponding Author: rajiabdulquadri24@gmail.com

Abstract: *The use of motorcycle as an alternative means of transportation has become dominant in cities of developing countries. This study examined motorcycle as a mode of passenger transport, pattern of operation, frequency and factors responsible for use as an alternative means of transportation in Ogbomoso, Oyo State, Nigeria. The sample size formula of Eichenberger et al. (2011) was adopted and data were collected using simple random sampling technique to administer 400 copies of questionnaires to motorcyclists at 15 survey points along 4 major traffic corridors. Informant interview was conducted on Chairmen of Amalgamated Commercial Motorcycle Riders Association of Nigeria (ACOMORAN) and Amalgamated National Commercial Motorcycle Workers Association (ANACOMWA) in Ogbomoso. Data on registered motorcycles were collected from ACOMORAN and ANACOMWA records. As at 2023, there were 14,697 registered commercial motorcycles with an average increase of 8.3% annually. Results showed that most (86%) of motorcycles were owned by the motorcyclists. The motorcycles were acquired through higher purchase (41%), outright purchase (32%), government assistance (14%) and cooperative loan (13%). Improved standard of living (40.5%), unemployment (24.8%), and source of income (15.0%) were the factors influencing motorcycle operation. Majority (42%) of motorcyclists operate throughout the week at morning period. The fares charged vary from ₦100 and above depending on length of journey. The study suggests local production of motorcycle and spare parts, education of motorcyclists on safety measures and enlightenment on road signs and symbols as well as other traffic rules among others.*

Keywords: Motorcycle Operation, Motorcyclists, Commuter, ACOMORAN and ANACOMWA

INTRODUCTION

The daily movement of people and goods in urban and rural areas is one of the most complex and difficult tasks facing public officials and transportation planners today (Tolley and Turton, 2014). The rising surge of traffic congestion auto-emitted pollution and accidents

seriously threaten the economic and social life of cities, and the fate of cities hinge on how wisely these urban movement problems can be resolved or at least minimized. Perboli et al. (2014), asserted that a city is as big and viable as its transportation systems which enable its people to move from one place to another and ensures even distribution of goods and services.

Therefore, the need to improve, develop and expand existing transport service is commonly on the development agenda of governments around the world, Nigerian inclusive (Abubakar and Aina, 2019). The situation is predicated on the fact that the demand for public transport services particularly in large towns and cities in developing countries, including Nigeria is quite high and growing to such an extent that the supply of public transport services usually does not meet its demand (Tirachini *et al.*, 2013).

The daily movement of people and goods in urban areas either regularly or occasionally at reasonable costs and time, as well with some assumed level of safety and comfort, makes transport one of the most pervasive activities in any society or economy (Redding and Turner, 2015). Therefore, the prevailing situation of short supply of public transport often attracts the attention of government, policy makers, planners as well as transport managers. This implies transport as an epitome of the complex relationship that exist, between the physical environment, pattern of social and political activity and the level of economic development (Odum and Aloba, 2014).

This assertion makes it difficult for government and all stakeholders in transport industry to handle transport issue with levity. One of the major interventions to avert this traffic problem is the introduction of motorcycle and other intermediate means of transport in order to improve intra city movement and ensure optimum mobility (Cohen and Kietzmann, 2014; World Health Organisation, 2015; Makarova *et al.*, 2016). The use of motorcycles has become dominant in city transport particularly in developing countries such as Nigeria as an alternative means of public transport.

The use of motorcycles for public transport is not an entirely new phenomenon in Nigeria. Before the late 1980s when the use of motorcycles for the public became widespread, motorcycle services had actually been provided for a fee or charge (Ukwayi *et al.*, 2013). The use of motorcycle first gained prominence in Cross River State in the 1970s where it was variously called “Aka-Uke” (Ademiluyi and Solanke, 2015).

However, in Nigeria, the use of motorcycle as continued to pose threats to life and properties to urban dwellers with socioeconomic impact which has been exacerbated by the economic activities in the country (Pojani and Stead, 2017; Aliyu and Amadu, 2017; Oli *et al.*, 2018). At the moment, many city managers and transport planners are inclined to show serious concern about the alarming and unprecedented rate at which motorcycles are being used for public transport in a growing number of Nigeria urban centres, with little or no regard for entry and quality control.

There are even serious doubts on whether there are legislative provisions that support the use of motorcycles for commercial purposes in several states of the federation. What is however clear is the implicit acceptance by most state governments that motorcycle operators can engage in moving people for an agreed sum of money? Any willing motorcyclist irrespective of his age, or ability or otherwise to ride with care can obtain a driver’s license or a hackney permit. The situation has grave consequences on the safety of motorcycle operators, their passengers and other innocent road users.

The attempt to fill the growing gap in public transport supply that brought about a spontaneous appearances and proliferation of commercial or public motorcycle in many Nigeria cities has assumed a worrisome dimension. Against the background of relatively

trend of using motorcycle as a modern and alternative means of public transport across urban and rural settlements. This study examined the use of motorcycle as a mode of passenger transport, ownership of motorcycle, factors responsible for use of motorcycle as an alternative mode of transport, pattern of operation, passenger fares and motorcyclists' monthly income in Ogbomoso, Oyo State, Nigeria.

STUDY AREA

Ogbomoso is an indigenous urban centre in Oyo State, Nigeria and has the characteristics of Yoruba settlement. Ogbomoso lies on latitude $8^{\circ} 15'$ North of the equator and longitude $4^{\circ} 15'$ east of the Greenwich Meridian. It is about 105 kilometres Northeast from Ibadan the capital of Oyo State and 53 kilometres Southwest of Ilorin, the capital of Kwara State as shown in Figure 1.

Motorcyclist association are variously named with each one claiming superiority over others. The association controlling the activities of registered motorcyclists in the study area are: Amalgamated Commercial Motorcycle Riders Association of Nigeria (ACOMORAN); and Amalgamated National Commercial Motorcycle Workers Association (ANACOMWA). These association are present in each local government area and divided into zones and each park has unit within the zones. Each zone coordinates the activities of its members. In addition, members of the union at unit and zonal levels are empowered to arrest and report any unregistered non-union motorcycle operators in their unit or zone. There is a total of 14,697 registered commercial motorcyclists in Ogbomoso as at December, 2023 (ACOMORAN and ANACOMWA, 2023). This figure was used as the sampling frame for the study.

Figure 1: Ogbomosho within the Context of Nigeria
 Source: Oyo State Ministry of Lands, Housing and Urban Development, 2023

METHODOLOGY

The total number of registered commercial motorcyclists (i.e., 14,697) was used as the sampling frame for the study. Thus, a total of four hundred (400) sample size was calculated using the sample size formula of Eichenberger et al. (2011) which is express as thus:

$$S = \frac{X^2NP(1-P)}{d^2(N-1) + X^2P(1-P)}$$

Where S represents the required sample size, X² is the table value of Chi-Square for 1 degree of freedom at the desired 0.95 confidence level

which is 3.841, N indicates the population size (14,697), P is the population proportion (assumed as 0.5 since this would provide the maximum sample size), while d is the degree of accuracy expressed as a proportion which is 5% (i.e., 0.05).

$$S = \frac{3.841 \times 14,697 \times 0.5 (1-0.5)}{0.0025 \times (14,697 - 1) \times 3.841 \times 0.5 (1-0.5)}$$

$$S = \frac{734850}{1837}$$

$$S = 400.027 \approx 400$$

This formula has been adopted by scholars such as Baba (2013), Charan & Biswas (2013) and Akinyode (2017). Thus, a total of 400 copies of questionnaires were administered randomly to motorcycle operators/motorcyclists along four (4) traffic corridors with fifteen (15) major motorcycle termini/stops as presented in Table 1. These points were identified through reconnaissance and informal discussion with

motorcycle operators. They were selected based on concentration of motorcycle operations. Interview was conducted on Chairmen of ACOMORAN and ANACOMWA in Ogbomosho to obtain information on the use of motorcycle and the number of registered motorcycles were obtained for a period of twelve (12) years from their records. Content analysis was used to analyse qualitative data acquired through interview.

Table 1: Survey Points and Questionnaire Administered

Traffic Corridor	Survey Point	No. of Points	Number Administered
Corridor A	Takie axis, LAUTECH, Oke Anu, Orita Naira, Isale Ora, Ile Ewe	6	100
Corridor B	Seminary axis, Akande market, High School, Aromole, Kajola	5	100
Corridor C	Ikoyi-Ile, Alaropo, Idi Ede, Oko Ile, Odo-Oba, Elegu, Ajawa, Otamokun	8	100
Corridor D	Iresaadu, Iregba, Gambari, Oko, Mayin, Iresaapa, Alayin	7	100
	Total	15	400

Source: Field Survey, 2024

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

MOTORCYCLE AS A MODE OF PASSENGER TRANSPORT IN OGBOMOSO

The use of motorcycle as a mode of public or passenger transport in Ogbomosho dates back to 1984 (ACCOMORAN Chairman). As observed by the general chairman of ACCOMORAN in Ogbomosho, the introduction started at Baptist

Medical/Baptist Theological Seminary Randa-Onitinrin village road junction. A location between the boundary of Ogbomosho North and Ogbomosho South Local Government Areas with just one middle age man of about 50 years old as at the time of its introductions with the man's old Rickety Suzuki 120 brand. This was due to inability and abandonment by commercial bus and taxi cab owners to ply and transport passengers and goods on the then deplorable road to their various destinations. Many other

roads that connect the township with the neighbouring village and town were also in bad condition.

Over time, the operation become well known after many other interested people mostly men, joined in the business and later launched their uniform and emblem in 1990 during their expanded meeting at Ogbomoso Town hall. Since then, remarkable growth has been witnessed and other village and towns within and around the Ogbomoso has established their own zonal unions. Presently, 14,697 motorcycles were registered in Ogbomoso up until 2023 (Table 2). The situation is better explained by the increasing rate of new motorcycles in Ogbomoso and its environs. The study observed that there is an average of 8.3% growth in the use of motorcycle as commercial operation in Ogbomoso within the span of twelve years (i.e., 2012-2023), with the year 2023 accounting for a major (13.4%) increase (Table 2 and Figure 2). This was influenced by higher purchase, government intervention in poverty alleviation

programme cooperative loan and personal savings which have made means of acquiring motorcycle for commercial operations (ACOMORAN and ANACOMWA Chairmen, Ogbomoso Zone). However, 2019 recorded the least number of commercial motorcycle registration with 975 registered commercial motorcycles. The increase in registered motorcycles from 1,397 in 2012 to 14,697 in 2023 shows an upsurge in motorcycle operation in the study area. This attributed to the benefits derived from the use of motorcycle as an alternative mode of passenger transport.

The study revealed that motorcycle operators ply both internal and external routes. The internal routes include all the routes within and across all the township while the external routes which interconnect small towns and villages include: Seminary/Bowen University Teaching Hospital (BUTH) - Onitinrin/Fapote route; Ora-Arowomole-Abede route; Mayin route; Isale Ora - Iresaapa route; Oke Anu - Abogunde route; Orita Naira-Soun High School-Jabata route; Sunsun - Otamokun rotue; and California - Ibapon Adindi route among others.

Table 2: Commercial Motorcycle Registration in Ogbomoso between 2012 and 2023

Year	Commercial Motorcycle	Percentage (%)	Average (%)
2012	1,397	9.5	
2013	1,201	8.2	
2014	1,104	7.5	
2015	1,302	8.9	
2016	1,121	7.6	
2017	1,000	6.8	
2018	1,193	8.1	8.3
2019	975	6.6	
2020	1,011	6.9	
2021	1,110	7.6	
2022	1,310	8.9	
2023	1,973	13.4	
Total	14,697	100.0	

Source: ACOMORAN and ANACOMWA, 2024

Figure 2: Trend of Motorcycle Registration in Ogbomoso (2012- 2023)
Source: ACOMORAN and ANACOMWA, 2024

OWNERSHIP OF MOTORCYCLE

Majority of motorcyclists (86%) were owners of the motorcycles they were riding at the time of the survey, while 14% of them were Hired-riders utilizing the daily return window (Figure 3). A large proportion (94.7%) of motorcycle owner owned one motorcycle and the remaining owned three (3.3%) and two (2.0%) motorcycles (Table 3). This implies that majority of the motorcycle operators utilized self-owned or personal motorcycle for their operations. While, there were only limited cases in which those who hired out motorcycle owned more than one motorcycles. Thus, majority of the motorcyclists (94.7%) owned one motorcycle. This presupposes that there is promising future for continued supply of motorcycle services in Ogbomoso. This is because the motorcycle will

automatically be available for public use and the system will be flourishing. It is also expected that there will be considerable expansion in their share of public market which means that their impact on the public motorcycles market is probably going to be increased from the current number of motorcycle operation.

The study also revealed that majority (41%) of the motorcycle operators acquired their motorcycles through higher purchase due to low financial capabilities (Table 4). Thirty-two percent (32%) acquired through outright purchase from their personal savings. The remaining acquired their motorcycle through government assistance (14%) and cooperative loan facility (13%). This conforms with the result of the interview conducted with both Chairmen of ACOMORAN and ANACOMWA

in Ogbomosho. As affirmed earlier in the study, they contended that higher purchase,

government intervention, cooperative loan and personal savings were they major means of motorcycle ownership in Ogbomosho.

Figure 3: Ownership Pattern of Commercial Motorcycle in Ogbomosho

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 3: Motorcycle Owned by Operators

Number	Frequency	Percentage (%)
One	379	94.7
Two	8	2.0
Three	13	3.3
Total	400	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 4: Means of Procurement of Commercial Motorcycle in the Study Area

Means of ownership	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Higher purchase	164	41.0
Government Assistance	56	14.0
Cooperative loan	52	13.0
Personal Saving	128	32.0
Total	400	100.0

Source: *Field Survey, 2024.*

FACTORS RESPONSIBLE FOR THE USE OF MOTORCYCLE AS AN ALTERNATIVE MODE OF TRANSPORT

The study examined the factors influencing the use motorcycle as an alternative mode of transport in Ogbomoso. It was observed that majority (40.5%) of the motorcycle operators ventured into the business to improve their standard of living in term of serving as a supplementary means of income to their primary source of income which includes farming, trading, teaching and artisanship (Table 5). These categories of operators affirmed that they seek financial means for their academic pursuit and acquiring equipment for their vocation. Twenty-four percent (24.8%) affirmed that unavailability of employment opportunities influenced their motorcycle operation. Most of those in this category are those who have completed their tertiary education and are job seekers. Some of the commercial motorcycle operators affirmed that the economic downturn in the country forced them to engage in motorcycle operation. For

instance, some of them sold their minibuses when they found it extremely difficult to afford the cost of their maintenance and used the proceeds to buy motorcycles for commercial purpose, in order to provide and take care of their families.

Primary source of income (15.0%) and lucrative form of business (15%) were the factors influencing motorcycle operation. Operators in this category neither have tertiary education nor learn any vocational activity. This prompted them to engaged in full-time public motorcycle operation. Few (4.7%) of the motorcycle operator indicated their desire to improve mobility of commuters as the reason for their commercial motorcycle operation. This implies that improve in standard of living of motorcyclists, unavailability of white-collar jobs, funding of academic activities, self-employment and alternative means to mobility of commuters are the factors influencing the use of motorcycle as an alternative means of transportation in the study area.

Table 5: Factors Influencing Motorcycle Operation in Ogbomosho

Factors	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Improve in standard of living motorcyclists	162	40.5
Unavailability of employment opportunities	99	24.8
Source of income	60	15.0
Lucrative form of business	60	15.0
Mobility of commuters	19	4.7
Total	400	100.0

Source: *Field Survey, 2024.*

PATTERN OF MOTORCYCLE OPERATION IN OGBOMOSO

On the modus operandi of motorcyclists in Ogbomosho, the study revealed that majority (58%) of motorcyclists operate in week days (i.e., Monday – Friday) particularly for motorcyclists operating along Seminary, Takie, Bowen University Teaching Hospital, LAUTECH Teaching Hospital and LAUTECH traffic corridor (Table 6). Therefore, it is not far-fetched that they offer their services civil servants, employees in the private sector and students who ply this traffic corridor majorly on working week days. The remaining (42%) motorcycle operator operates every day of the week. As evidenced from the study, variation exists in time of daily operation of motorcyclists. A large proportion (72%) operates at all time of the day, 18% operates at afternoon periods only, 8% operates at morning periods only and the remaining (2%) operates at evening time only. This presupposes that the motorcycle Operators that operates all time of the day engage in full time motorcycle operation, while, the remaining that operate at different time of the day were part-time motorcyclists that engage in commercial motorcycle operation as a means for alternative source of income to improve standard of living,

funding of academic activities or as a means for acquiring vocational equipment for their learned artisan Trade (Table 6).

Like most para-transit services, motorcycle operators in Ogbomosho either operate fixed route or flexible services. The study also showed that majority (68.6%) of motorcyclists operates flexible services with no fixed route. They ply between two to five routes within their area of operation. As expected, majority chose routes that were quite remunerative and those with fairly good roads and high frequency of commuters. Also, queue at terminus of fixed route deter majority of motorcyclists operating flexible services particularly at off-peak periods with low turnout of commuters. The remaining (31.4%) operates a fixed route services and is influenced by the office they hold as members of the executives of their respective union (Table 6). This is in a bid to be readily available to attends to matters affecting members of their association. Full-time motorcycle operators plying fixed routes were making on the average, between 25 to 40 trips in a day. The reason or this high number of turnarounds is perhaps because only one passenger is carried at a time and usually straight to his or her destination.

Table 6: Pattern of Motorcycle Operation in Ogbomosho

Weekly Operation	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Monday – Sunday	168	42.0
Monday - Friday	232	58.0
Total	400	100.0
Time of Operation	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Morning	32	8.0
Afternoon	72	18.0
Evening	8	2.0
Throughout the day	288	72.0
Total	400	100.0
Route of Operation	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Fixed route	126	31.4
Flexible service	274	68.6
Total	400	100

Source: *Field Survey, 2024*

FREQUENCY IN THE USE OF MOTORCYCLE AS ALTERNATIVE MEANS OF TRANSPORT IN OGBOMOSO

A large proportion (57.7%) of commuters in Ogbomosho regularly utilized motorcycle as an alternative mean of transport. This might be influenced by traffic congestion that is usually witnessed during the morning and evening peak periods along major traffic corridors such as Seminary – LAUTECH and Takie – Owode traffic corridors among others, flexibility in motorcycle operation and ability to offer door-to-door services as compared to minibuses that is used as a major means of public transport in the city. This presupposes that majority of commuters were very regular users of motorcycle as a public transport. While, few (29%) of the commuters occasionally utilize motorcycle as a means of transport.

PASSENGER FARES AND OPERATORS' MONTHLY INCOME

The fares that motorcycle operators charge tend to vary sometimes and it is also negotiable.

Nevertheless; it was discovered that motorcycle operators were charging more over the same distance than their counterparts operating minibus and tricycle. The reasons often put forward for charging relatively higher fares include; disembarking passengers right at their door-step or destination, inability to sometimes get passengers to carry on return journey and bad roads along some routes. From LAUTECH to Takie or Bowen University Teaching Hospital or interior of the city, minibuses charge ₦150 as against the ₦300 by motorcyclist per rider or drop. Elsewhere, the minimum in charge was ₦100 depending on the length of the trip. Passengers' fares tend to be stable for services provided along fixed routes, whereas, fares are usually negotiated where a passenger on request, wants to be driven to a specific destination or on chartered services. It is therefore shown that it is an income generating venture and many people through this means make their living and thereby not only alleviating poverty but also reducing the rate of criminal activities among the people in the study area. Besides, some of them have

been able to save and invest their money or proceeds to diversify to other businesses.

The study showed that Operators make between ₦ 5,000 and ₦ 15,000 daily which amount to between ₦ 150,000 and ₦ 450,000 per month. In simple term, 66%, 31% and 5% of the operators can get above ₦ 30,000, between ₦ 150,000 to ₦ 300,000 and less than ₦ 105,000 respectively

on monthly basis despite the charge rate of between ₦ 100 to ₦ 300 per trip within the study area (Table 7). The highest take-home pay may be attributed to those who engage in the operation as full-time operators. The second category belongs to either those who operate in the morning and evening while those in third category are those who operate as casual riders. These are the amounts realized after all other expenses on fuel and vehicle maintenance.

Table 7: Monthly Income of Operators

Daily Income (₦)	Monthly Income (₦)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
5,000	150,000	12	3.0
5,000-15,000	150,000-450,000	124	31.0
Above 15,000	<450,000	264	66.0
	Total	400	100.0

Source *Field Survey, 2024*.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concluded that there is an annual increase in the number of commercial motorcycles registered in Ogbomosho due to its flexible nature and ability to offer door-to-door services. This has made motorcycle to be widely used as an alternative means of transportation in Ogbomosho particularly during morning and evening peak periods with high passenger traffic along major traffic corridors such as Seminary-LAUTECH traffic corridor. Its operation is pronounced every day of the week (Monday – Friday). Motorcyclists operates on fixed and flexible routes depending on commuter traffic, road condition and queuing time at off-peak periods. The minimum fee payable by commuter is ₦100 depending on the travel distance and the price increase as the travel distance increases.

The study recommended local assembling of motorcycle and its spare parts in order to meet the increasing use of motorcycle as an alternative means of transport. Also recommended is the provision of credits facilities by government and financial institutions to motorcycle operators through their registered unions. This will also ease the purchase of motorcycle for commercial operation by intending motorcyclists in order to meet the demand for motorcycle as an alternative mode of transports particularly at peak periods. Motorcycle operators needs to be educated on safe mode of operation and use of major traffic corridors particularly at peak periods in order to ensure the safety of motorcyclist and their passenger.

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